

Research Protocol

Adaptive Quality of Service Management in Energy-Constrained IoT Networks: A Systematic Literature Review

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1. Introduction and Rationale

The Internet of Things (IoT) connects billions of battery-powered devices that must balance Quality of Service (QoS) requirements against strict energy constraints. Despite a growing body of research on adaptive QoS mechanisms for energy-constrained IoT networks, the literature remains fragmented across multiple domains, terminologies, and solution approaches. No existing review provides a unified, PRISMA-compliant synthesis that simultaneously covers multiple IoT network architectures, algorithmic categories, QoS parameters, and energy optimization objectives. This protocol describes the methodology for conducting such a systematic literature review.

2. Objectives

The review aims to:

- (1) Categorize adaptive QoS management approaches into distinct algorithmic classes (classical optimization, machine learning, deep learning, metaheuristics, heuristic/rule-based, and hybrid methods);
- (2) Analyze the distribution of research effort across IoT network types, QoS parameters, and algorithmic approaches;
- (3) Evaluate the evidence supporting specific adaptation mechanisms and identify which are backed by real-world testing;
- (4) Track the growth of emerging approaches (ML, DL, edge/fog computing) relative to classical optimization;
- (5) Quantify structural deficits, including the cross-layer optimization gap and security co-optimization rate;
- (6) Assess the state of security–QoS co-optimization; and
- (7) Propose a structured research roadmap addressing priority gaps with concrete directions.

3. Research Questions

- RQ1** What types of IoT networks and energy constraints are addressed in the literature, and how are energy limitations managed?
- RQ2** What QoS parameters and performance metrics are considered in energy-constrained IoT networks?
- RQ3** What adaptation mechanisms and algorithmic approaches are used for QoS management?
- RQ4** How do proposed solutions adapt to changing network conditions and varying device capabilities?
- RQ5** What evaluation methodologies, metrics, and testbeds are used to validate adaptive QoS solutions?

4. Search Strategy

4.1 Databases

Four primary databases will be searched: Scopus, Web of Science, IEEE Xplore, and ScienceDirect. Supplementary searches will be conducted through SpringerLink, Google Scholar, and ACM Digital Library.

4.2 Search Period

January 2018 to December 2025.

4.3 Search String

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("Quality of Service" OR "QoS management" OR "QoS routing")  
AND ("Internet of Things" OR "IoT" OR "Wireless Sensor Networks" OR "WSN")  
AND ("Energy efficiency" OR "Energy-aware" OR "Energy-constrained" OR "Power  
consumption")  
AND ("Adaptive" OR "Dynamic" OR "Self-adaptive" OR "Real-time adaptation")
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5. Eligibility Criteria

5.1 Inclusion Criteria

- (IC1) Address both QoS management and energy efficiency/constraints in IoT or WSN environments;
- (IC2) Present an adaptive or dynamic approach for QoS optimization;
- (IC3) Published in a peer-reviewed journal or conference proceedings;
- (IC4) Written in English;
- (IC5) Have a DOI or be indexed in Scopus or Web of Science;
- (IC6) Published between 2018 and 2025; and
- (IC7) Include empirical validation via simulation, testbed, or theoretical analysis with concrete results.

5.2 Exclusion Criteria

- (EC1) Address QoS without any energy consideration;
- (EC2) Focus on energy efficiency without QoS focus;
- (EC3) Present only theoretical contributions without empirical validation;
- (EC4) Target non-IoT domains;
- (EC5) Written in a language other than English;
- (EC6) Editorial notes, opinion articles, or duplicates; or
- (EC7) Lack sufficient detail for quality assessment.

6. Study Selection Process

The selection follows a four-stage PRISMA flow:

Stage	Description	Expected output
1. Identification	Initial search across all databases	~2,700 records
2. Deduplication	Remove duplicate records	~2,100 unique records
3. Screening	Title and abstract screening against IC/EC	~380 potentially relevant

4. Eligibility	Full-text assessment of all criteria	Final corpus for analysis
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Screening will be performed independently by three reviewers (H.A., E.E., Y.F.). Inter-rater reliability will be assessed using Fleiss' Kappa on a stratified random sample of approximately 20% of the corpus. Disagreements will be resolved through consensus discussion.

7. Data Extraction

For each retained article, the following data will be extracted using a standardized form:

Category	Fields
Publication metadata	Title, authors, journal, year, DOI, Scimago quartile
Study characteristics	IoT network type, QoS parameters addressed, energy constraints
Methodological details	Adaptation approach, algorithms, techniques used
Evaluation information	Metrics, simulation tool, testbed details, performance results

8. Quality Assessment

Each article will be evaluated on methodological rigor, validation approach, reproducibility, and relevance to the five research questions. A multi-criteria quality scoring framework will assess four dimensions:

- (a) Breadth of QoS scope (1 parameter = low, 2 = moderate, 3+ = high);
- (b) Algorithmic category and sophistication;
- (c) Validation type (simulation only vs. testbed/real deployment); and
- (d) Whether security is considered alongside QoS and energy.

9. Data Synthesis and Analysis

The analysis will be organized along five dimensions:

- Classification by IoT network type (WSN, edge/MEC, fog, 5G/6G, SDN-IoT, IIoT, IoMT, LPWAN, UAV, IoV);
- QoS parameter coverage analysis (latency, reliability, throughput, network lifetime, availability, packet loss, coverage, jitter);
- Algorithmic taxonomy (classical optimization, ML, DL, metaheuristics, heuristic/rule-based, hybrid);
- Energy optimization objectives (consumption reduction, efficiency, resource optimization, lifetime maximization, transmission optimization, load balancing); and
- Cross-analysis mapping algorithmic approaches to network types.

Results will be presented through frequency tables, cross-tabulation matrices, and visualizations (bar charts, bubble charts, heatmaps, donut charts, PRISMA flow diagram).

10. Protocol Amendments

Any substantive amendments to this protocol made during the conduct of the review will be documented, dated, and justified in the final published review.

11. Key References

- [1] Page, M.J. et al. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ*, 372, n71.
- [2] Fleiss, J.L. (1971). Measuring nominal scale agreement among many raters. *Psychological Bulletin*, 76(5), 378–382.
- [3] Cohen, J. (1960). A coefficient of agreement for nominal scales. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 20(1), 37–46.
- [4] Landis, J.R. & Koch, G.G. (1977). The measurement of observer agreement for categorical data. *Biometrics*, 33(1), 159–174.